

DECARBONISING HEALTHCARE IN LMICS: THE ROLE OF ENERGY

Introduction

It is widely recognised that climate change represents a threat to public health and a massive amplifier of inequalities worldwide [Costello et al. (2009)].

At present, climate change represents a significant challenge to both environmental and health equity [Rossati (2017)], posing serious concerns about the adverse inter-generational effects arising from these inequalities.

Therefore, globally, governments are required to act swiftly to curb emissions, which are currently progressing at such a pace that even the most ambitious measures to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change will no longer be enough to stop it. Parallel to the challenges of reducing emissions in the medium-long term, governments are also required to act in the short-run to increase adaption to the adverse effects already produced by climate change to reduce the vulnerability of populations and protect the health of people around the world [Romanello et al. (2021)].

In this complex framework, the healthcare sector has a primary role: dealing with the consequences of climate change and being an active player in making our societies less polluting. A recent study estimated the sector may account for about 4-5% of total global emissions (or, in absolute terms, for 2-2.4 Gt of CO₂ emissions) [Rasheed et al. (2021)].

Pursuing climate resilience will make health systems more capable of protecting and enhancing population health at multiple levels (i.e., local, regional, national, and global levels) “*in an unstable and changing climate*” [WHO (2021)].

Therefore, the challenge for healthcare administrators worldwide shall be to identify and address vulnerabilities of health systems and choose actions to increase their resilience while balancing investments in climate-change adaptation and mitigation strategies, among other pressing public health agendas which compete for both human resources and public financing. In this context, it must be considered that high average emissions-intensity levels characterise health systems in LMICs. Therefore, achieving universal health coverage in those countries would not only require a sensible increase in resources committed by those countries but could result in a substantial increase in the carbon footprint of the healthcare sector worldwide if the average emissions-intensity levels for those countries remain stable at the current levels [Rasheed et al. (2021)].

Literature overview

The effects of climate change are manifest and extensively documented, as are the consequences for human health.

Climate change has been clearly shown to impact the burden of three major communicable diseases (i.e., HIV, tuberculosis, and malaria), which continue to be leading causes of mortality and morbidity in many LMICs. Anyway, beyond the well-documented effects on infectious diseases, climate change can be held responsible for a broader range of threats to human health, including injuries during natural disasters, malnutrition, and increased mortality during periods of sub-optimal ambient temperature due to complications in chronic patients [Rossati (2017)].

Interestingly, although health systems are at the forefront of addressing the adverse health effects of climate-related shocks and stressors, their operations often impact the environment and the health of populations due to the management of waste, energy and water and the pollution produced by the supply chain [WHO (2021)]. Therefore, achieving emissions-free

provision of essential health care calls for action on these aspects, given that improving access and accessibility to climate-resilient and environmentally sustainable care ultimately means strengthening health systems' ability to offer high-quality care and assistance to people and guarantee better economic sustainability, reducing the costs of structures [WHO (2021)].

In LMICs, public healthcare infrastructure and services are of major importance because, in general, people have very tight budget constraints which limit individual private spending on healthcare. Therefore, the burden of poverty and disease is shifted mainly toward public health expenditure in those countries [Saleem et al. (2021)].

Access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy (UN SDG 7) represents a vital feature for wider social development, improved quality of life and increased income possibilities for people but also to pursue universal health coverage (UN SDG 3) [WB (2013)].

The WHO lists several benefits from stable energy provision in health facilities, distinguishing between direct benefits (e.g., improved care for patients and decreased mortality) and indirect benefits (e.g., increased staff attention and better working conditions) [WHO 2014]. Many health facilities in LMICs, however, do not have access to a reliable and affordable source of energy for essential services and that reduces diagnostic capabilities as well as the number and quality of therapeutic services provided [Franco et al. (2017)] and it also limits operating hours to daytime undermining continuous acceptance and treatment of patients during night [Olatomiwa (2016)]. To have an idea of the cost of the lack of access to stable energy provision, Fofana et al. (2022) estimate that, for each 10 per cent increase in access to electricity in the Sub-Saharan Africa region, six children could be saved per 1,000 live births.

In LMICs, many facilities are not connected to the central power grid. They must rely on fuel generators, which have lower installation costs but require polluting fuels that exacerbate negative health outcomes and often have higher operating costs. In those contexts, the use of decentralised power sources (especially renewable energy sources that have the potential to

provide clean and cost-effective electricity) can play a huge role in electrifying healthcare facilities.

Once access to a stable and reliable energy supply has been provided, the subsequent step should be to invest to improve energy efficiency and decrease emissions. Naturally, healthcare facilities' primary objective is to provide care to improve health [Golbazi and Aktas (2020)] and offer shelters for displaced communities during extreme weather events and natural disasters. But, although energy efficiency may not rank among the primary objectives of a healthcare facility, still there might be solid arguments in its favour like the possibility of realising operational cost savings to be re-invested for the replacement of medical assets and the day-to-day operation as obsolescence in equipment, systems and buildings contribute to high electricity consumption and therefore to higher daily operational costs [Balbus et al. (2016)].

The evaluation of the adequate energy-production solution should be based on the careful analysis of different factors like the type and dimension of the facility, its location in terms of connection to the central power grid, the availability of affordable fuel provision, geo-climatic conditions to identify the potential of different renewable energy sources [Franco et al. (2017)].

Conclusion

Climate change is already imposing severe consequences on health, and its burden is probably destined to increase further, faster and irretrievably.

Coordinated strategies to contrast and mitigate climate change and implement actions to adapt to already produced changes must be implemented worldwide. At the same time, it is important to consider that future health impacts of climate change will largely depend on the long-term effects of already triggered climate modifications and on the effectiveness of adaptation and mitigation actions already implemented.

The present essay aims to argue that energy access and management in healthcare facilities can play a relevant role in fighting against climate change while also achieving (better) health for all.

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